

SETTING UP OF PULL-OUT TEST AT IMPACT STRAIN RATES FOR SMA WIRE/pCBT ADAPTIVE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

The interfacial strength of NiTi wires/pCBT composite for impact applications has been studied. These materials are strain rate dependent, so that the effect of this parameter on the interfacial strength has been characterized by a new pull-out test method. The interfacial strength increases with the strain rate and is high enough to induce the stress induced martensitic transformation in the NiTi wires.

Keywords: SMA; pCBT; RTM; Impact; Interface strength.

INTRODUCTION

The high recoverable strain (6%) and the great energy dissipation capability of the Shape Memory Alloys (SMA) are favourable to be used as reinforcement in composite materials for improving the damage resistance at low impact velocities [1-3]. For these applications, SMAs have been commonly embedded into an inherently brittle (break strain < 1%) thermoset matrix, so the best performances of SMAs have not yet been harnessed. Thermoplastic polymers are potentially better since they are more ductile and tougher. However, their main drawback is the high melt viscosity. The fabrication process may be enhanced lowering the melt viscosity to ensure the correct positioning of the reinforcements and ensuring that the matrix completely wets the reinforcement surface. This may be reached during the fabrication process with a very low viscosity matrix like pCBT. The water-like viscosity of this thermoplastic material is achieved by reactive polymerization [4]. Regarding the interfacial characterization, the single fibre pull-out test is commonly used to determine the interfacial strength of the fibre-matrix interface. This test has been applied mainly to the interface characterization of SMA/thermoset composites [5-8], and only a few works deal with the characterization of SMA/thermoplastic interface often making the comparison with the thermoset matrix [9,10]. The debonding strain rate achieved during this conventional test may be considered within the quasi-static range, with maximum strain rates achieved of 0.5 mm/s [11]. Being SMAs [12] and polymers strain rate dependent, the quasi-static pull-out characterization is not valid for the development of new composite materials for impact applications. Therefore, it is essential to have some measures of the interfacial bond strength between the SMA wire and the host matrix at impact strain rates.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

Materials and specimens

Prepolymer (CBT160[®]) was supplied in form of pellets by Cyclics[®] Corporation, which after polymerization forms the engineering thermoplastic polybutylene terephthalate (pCBT). The reinforcement is a commercially available NiTi SMA, ref. NT09, purchased from @medical technologies (AMT). The material was supplied in the form of wire, 0.5 mm in diameter, showing superelastic behaviour at room temperature. Two different finish surface conditions were analysed to enhance the surface roughness, sandblasted and pickled. The manufacturing process of the specimens is as follows. The melted pCBT resin was poured into the mould previously heated to 240 °C and in which the NiTi wires were positioned conveniently so that they were embedded 8 mm in the pCBT matrix (6 x 12 x 20 mm³). The temperature was kept constant 20 min before water quenching.

Experimental set-up

For quasi-static tests, specimens were tested in a uniaxial screw-driven testing machine Instron 4206, and displacement controlled tension tests were conducted at strain rate of 10^{-4} s^{-1} . For the impact experiments, a pendulum with an impactor mass is released from certain height in order to achieve the initial impact velocity, figure 1a. All the tests have been carried out at room temperature. The pull-out specimen must be fixed between a mobile grip and a fixed grip, and when the impactor reaches the lowest point it hits the mobile grip, figure 1b, transmitting the impact energy to the interface.

Figure 1. Experimental set up for pull-out test at impact strain rates, a) general view, b) detail of the specimen attachment .

The tensile force transmitted to the sample, $F(t)$, is measured at the fixed grip by a piezoelectric sensor and stored in an oscilloscope before conditioning the signal with a charge amplifier. The displacement of the mobile grip $\delta(t)$, may be calculated from the force-time data ($F(t)$) by two successive integrations, equation 1, where V_0 is the initial impact velocity and m is the mass of the impactor. The impactor mass employed was 1.098 kg and was released from an initial height so that the impact velocity was 3.7 m/s being the initial strain rate $2 \times 10^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The velocity evolution, $V(t)$, may also be calculated from the force-time data, equation 2.

$$\delta(t) = \int_0^t \left(V_0 - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^t F(t) dt \right) dt \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

$$V(t) = V_0 - \frac{1}{m} \int_0^t F(t) dt \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interfacial strength is higher at impact than at quasi-static strain rates, figure 2, and in both cases it is higher than necessary to induce the martensitic transformation by stress in NiTi wires, as is evidenced by the appearance of the transformation plateau stress zones. The plateau strength is higher at impact because of the self-heating process due to the exothermic character of the direct SIM transformation [12]. While at low strain rates there is enough time to release all the heat generated during the martensitic transformation to the surroundings, at impact, the time is drastically reduced ($< 1\text{ms}$) being the deformation process totally adiabatic so that the transformation heat cannot be released from the reinforcements and is spent in warming up them increasing the transformation stress.

Figure 2. Pull-out test of NiTi wires embedded in pCBT matrix. a) at quasi-static strain rate. b) at impact strain rate.

Regarding the strain rate evolution during the pull-out impact test, it is worth to mention that while during the conventional pull-out test carried out at low strain rates the displacement may be controlled and constant velocity may be achieved during the deformation; for the impact test only the initial velocity may be set up being its evolution during the test uncontrolled with a decreasing trend due to the energy losses. Nevertheless, this decrement in velocity, calculated from the equation 2, is lower than 2% for the configuration applied in the present work, as is shown in figure 3, so that the impact velocity during the test may be considered constant.

Figure 3. Velocity evolution during the impact pull-out test.

The higher interface strength shown at impact for the sandblasted wires, figure 2b, may be a consequence of its higher roughness as is evidenced in the fractographic analysis via SEM observations. While the roughness shape of the pickled reinforcement appears preferentially in the circumferential direction of the wire, in the sandblasted wire this is more uniform, figure 4.

Figure 4. As received NiTi wire reinforcement roughness, a) sandblasted, b) pickled.

Nevertheless, the pull-out mechanism between pCBT and NiTi at low strain rates does not seem to depend significantly on the surface finish conditions as is evidenced in figure 2a. Despite the greater roughness shape on the longitudinally direction of the sandblasted wire, the remaining pCBT matrix adhered to the wire after the test is distributed in a similar way whichever the surface finish conditions of the reinforcement is. In any of case, the pCBT matrix is pulled-out locally in an homogeneous way, arising zones ($< 200 \mu\text{s}$) where the matrix, in white in figure 5, has been torn away from the reinforcement.

On the contrary, the remaining pCBT matrix adhered to the wires for the impact tests show different distributions than at low strain rates showing pulled out fibres of pCBT

still adhered to the reinforcements, figure 6. This may explain the differences in interfacial strength at impact than at low strain rates shown in figure 2. Moreover, the distribution of pCBT observed in figure 6 is also influenced by the surface finish condition which may change the interfacial shear strength as is shown for the impact pull-out tests of the figure 2b. The lower roughness shape on the longitudinally direction of the pickled reinforcement may assist the matrix debonding in the axial direction as is shown in the detail of figure 6b.

Figure 5. NiTi/pCBT interface failure surface loaded at low strain rates (0.15 mm/min), a) sandblasted, b) pickled.

Figure 6. NiTi/pCBT interface failure surface loaded at impact strain rates (3.7 m/s) a) sandblasted, b) pickled.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed pull-out test is able to characterize the interfacial strength at the intermediate impact strain-rate range. This test has been applied successfully to the characterization of the NiTi wire/pCBT interface, showing higher interfacial strength at impact than at quasi-static strain rates due to different pull-out mechanisms observed. The interfacial strength dependence on the surface finish condition is greater at impact strain rates.

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